

ZENODO openAIRE e-publishing - Paid for by the European Union powered by CERN (Organisation Européenne pour la Recherche Nucléaire)

Hamid Salari, David Seideman, Ali Asgari, Carolina Diamandis

LCG RESEARCH

Correspondence to diamandis@lazar-consortium.com

Preliminary report

Aspirin - Rediscovering the Potency of an Age-Old Medication

We present a case involving a middle-aged male patient undergoing treatment for Oshtoran Syndrome, a rare and complex condition characterized by an array of over 85 symptoms. Initially, the very ill patient was administered a high-dose regimen of Prednisolone, demonstrating significant efficacy in controlling key symptoms. However, prolonged use led to the development of Cushing's syndrome, necessitating a drastic reduction of Prednisolone by 95%. This reduction significantly compromised our primary strategy for managing the condition's symptoms.

In search of alternative treatments capable of offering symptomatic relief without the adverse effects associated with high-dose corticosteroids, we initially trialed high-dose Naproxen, which did not yield significant clinical improvement. During this challenging period, aspirin emerged as a surprising and effective alternative.^{6,9} This ancient medication demonstrated unexpected efficacy in managing a significant portion of the symptoms

previously controlled by Prednisolone. The shift to aspirin mitigated the risk of further steroid-induced severe complications and underscored the potential of older, well-established medications in treating complex, modern medical conditions.

By chance, the introduction of aspirin (1-1-1) into the patient's regimen led to a remarkable control of approximately 60% of the symptoms initially managed by Prednisolone, marking a serendipitous pivot in our treatment approach. The employment of "biologic drugs" was not considered viable due to the syndrome's pathology, which features a multitude of molecular targets not precisely addressed by the mechanisms of these often helpful medications.⁸ Additionally, the complexity of managing this patient was amplified by a regimen that includes a total of 14 different medications, emphasizing the need for a meticulously tailored and closely monitored treatment plan.

Unique Pharmacological Profile of Aspirin

Aspirin is distinguished from other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) by its ability to irreversibly inhibit cyclooxygenase (COX) enzymes. This leads to a sustained decrease in prostaglandin and thromboxane synthesis, offering both anti-inflammatory and antiplatelet effects, the latter of which is unique to aspirin among NSAIDs and crucial for its role in preventing cardiovascular events.

Aspirin also influences immune function beyond COX inhibition, potentially modulating the activity of NF- κ B, a protein complex involved in DNA transcription and cytokine

production. This could be pivotal in managing the immune dysregulation aspects of various conditions.

Emerging evidence suggests aspirin and its metabolites might affect mitochondrial function, which could be particularly relevant given the role of mitochondrial dysfunction in many syndromes. This may involve protection against oxidative stress or modulation of mitochondrial metabolism. Aspirin's potential neuroprotective effects could stem from its anti-inflammatory actions in the central nervous system or effects on cerebral blood flow, underscored by its effective penetration of the blood-brain barrier (BBB) compared to other NSAIDs.

Aspirin's irreversible inhibition of COX-1 leads to a lasting reduction in thromboxane A₂ production, inhibiting platelet aggregation and blood clot formation.

This unique pharmacological profile positions aspirin as a particularly useful agent in conditions associated with an elevated risk of inflammation and potentially thrombosis, underscoring its serendipitous yet important role in the management of complex medical conditions. Beyond the COX inhibition, aspirin has been shown to influence immune function in more complex ways, such as modulating the activity of protein complexes involved in DNA transcription and cytokine production. This might help manage the immune dysregulation aspects of many low-grade inflammatory situations.

There is also emerging evidence that aspirin and its metabolites might affect mitochondrial function, which could be particularly relevant when mitochondrial dysfunction is an issue. This could involve protection against oxidative stress or the modulation of mitochondrial metabolism. Aspirin has even been investigated for its potential neuroprotective effects. This could be due to its anti-inflammatory actions in the central nervous system or effects on cerebral blood flow. It is important to remember that Aspirin passes the blood-brain barrier (BBB) way more effectively than the NSAIDs.

Aspirin irreversibly inhibits COX-1, leading to a lasting reduction in thromboxane A₂ production, thereby inhibiting platelet

aggregation and blood clot formation. This effect can be particularly beneficial in conditions associated with an increased tendency towards inflammation and potentially thrombosis. In contrast, Naproxen inhibits COX-1 reversibly and may, therefore, be less effective in modulating platelet function.

While both Aspirin and Naproxen can inhibit COX enzymes, Aspirin uniquely modulates COX-2 in a way that leads to the production of lipoxins, which possess anti-inflammatory and resolution-promoting properties. This conversion can contribute to the resolution of inflammatory reactions and could be advantageous for patients with chronic or autoimmune inflammatory conditions.

Aspirin may also exert specific effects on the immune system beyond COX enzyme inhibition. It has been shown to influence the production of IL-4 and IL-10, fostering a shift towards an anti-inflammatory immune response. These immunomodulatory effects could be particularly relevant in treating diseases and syndromes, where autoimmune-like processes play a role.

Aspirin also induces the production of Aspirin-Triggered Lipoxins (ATLs), a class of lipids with strong anti-inflammatory and resolution-promoting properties. These lipoxins can contribute to immune system regulation and resolve inflammation more effectively than the mechanisms mediated by Naproxen or other NSAIDs.^{9,13,14,14,15,16,17,18,19}

Safety

While gastrointestinal risks are a concern with both Aspirin and other NSAIDs like Naproxen, it is pertinent to approach these risks with vigilance. The dose of Aspirin needed for the above mentioned effects is somewhere between 1500mg and 2500mg daily. It falls within the recommended guidelines for adults in many countries, allowing us to work with the drug without venturing into off-label territory.²⁰

Clinical Implications

This experience illuminates the profound importance of individualized treatment strategies. The discovery of Aspirin's efficacy,

where other NSAIDs and potential biologic treatments have fallen short, underscores the necessity for both innovative thinking and a solid understanding of pharmacological principles in patient management.¹⁻¹⁹

Conclusion

In the specific instance at hand, the intricacies inherent in the patient's syndrome - which is marked by a plethora of potential intervention points without a definitive guide to the most critical targets - necessitated a departure from biologic treatments. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that situations such as ours are not outliers; they represent the norm in medical practice. Our patient's condition, along with those of numerous others, challenges the efficacy of the selective targeting strategies employed by the so-called blockbuster immunological biologic drugs. These drugs often find their way into prescription protocols not due to their unassailable suitability but because alternatives seem scarce. Thus, it becomes imperative for non-profit research entities and academic institutions worldwide to re-evaluate the multifaceted, venerable drug known as Aspirin. The need for further investigation by organizations equipped with more extensive resources than our own is pressing. Surprisingly, Aspirin - a drug with a long-standing history - continues to exhibit considerable, yet-to-be-explored potential, affirming the dynamic and progressive essence of medical science. This insight mandates a refreshed scrutiny of established pharmaceuticals, particularly when confronted with clinical scenarios that defy conventional therapeutic approaches.

Conflict of interests

None

References

1. Görög P, Kovács IB. Impaired red cell deformability in established adjuvant arthritic disease in rats. *Agents Actions*. 1980 Nov;10(5):427-30. doi: 10.1007/BF01968041. PMID: 7211576.
2. Antiinflammatory drugs. *Arthritis Rheum*. 1970 Sep-Oct;13(5):594-8. PMID: 4921537.
3. Zhao M, Chang C, Liu Z, Chen LM, Chen Q. Treatment with low-dose aspirin increased the level LIF and integrin $\beta 3$ expression in mice during the implantation window. *Placenta*. 2010 Dec;31(12):1101-5. doi: 10.1016/j.placenta.2010.10.002. Epub 2010 Oct 29. PMID: 21035850.
4. Hawkey CJ. COX-2 inhibitors. *Lancet*. 1999 Jan 23;353(9149):307-14. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(98)12154-2. PMID: 9929039.
5. Vane JR. The mechanism of action of anti-inflammatory drugs. *Ernst Schering Res Found Workshop*. 2000;(31):1-23. PMID: 10943325.
6. Segre EJ, Chaplin M, Forchielli E, Runkel R, Sevelius H. Naproxen-aspirin interactions in man. *Clin Pharmacol Ther*. 1974 Apr;15(4):374-9. doi: 10.1002/cpt.1974154374. PMID: 4821440.
7. Namazy JA, Simon RA. Sensitivity to nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. *Ann Allergy Asthma Immunol*. 2002 Dec;89(6):542-50; quiz 550, 605. doi: 10.1016/S1081-1206(10)62099-6. PMID: 12487218.
8. Baldo, B. A. (n.d.). *Safety of Biologics Therapy: Monoclonal Antibodies, Cytokines, Fusion Proteins, Hormones, Enzymes, Coagulation Proteins, Vaccines, Botulinum Toxins*. Deutschland: Springer International Publishing.
9. Schafer AI. Effects of nonsteroidal antiinflammatory drugs on platelet function and systemic hemostasis. *J Clin Pharmacol*. 1995 Mar;35(3):209-19. doi: 10.1002/j.1552-4604.1995.tb04050.x. PMID: 7608308.
10. Gilroy DW, Perretti M. Aspirin and steroids: new mechanistic findings and avenues for drug discovery. *Curr Opin Pharmacol*. 2005 Aug;5(4):405-11. doi: 10.1016/j.coph.2005.02.006. PMID: 15955733.
11. Berk M, Dean O, Drexhage H, McNeil JJ, Moylan S, O'Neil A, Davey CG, Sanna L, Maes M. Aspirin: a review of its neurobiological properties and therapeutic potential for mental illness. *BMC Med*. 2013 Mar 18;11:74. doi: 10.1186/1741-7015-11-74. PMID: 23506529; PMCID: PMC3751197.
12. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3751197/pdf/1741-7015-11-74.pdf>
13. Raison CL, Rutherford RE, Woolwine BJ, Shuo C, Schettler P, Drake DF, Haroon E, Miller AH: A Randomized controlled trial

of the tumor necrosis factor antagonist infliximab for treatment-resistant depression: the role of baseline inflammatory biomarkers. *Arch Gen Psychiatry* 2012, 1-11.

14. Leonard B, Maes M. Mechanistic explanations how cell-mediated immune activation, inflammation and oxidative and nitrosative stress pathways and their sequels and concomitants play a role in the pathophysiology of unipolar depression. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2012 Feb;36(2):764-85. doi: 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2011.12.005. Epub 2011 Dec 19. PMID: 22197082.
15. Jaturapatporn D, Isaac MG, McCleery J, Tabet N. Aspirin, steroidal and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2012 Feb 15; (2): CD006378. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD006378.pub2. PMID: 22336816.
16. Sachdeva S, Saluja H, Mani A, Phadnaik MB, Mani S. Lipoxins in inflammation. *Clin Hemorheol Microcirc.* 2022;82(3):201-216. doi: 10.3233/CH-211346. PMID: 35147530.
17. Hussain M, Javeed A, Ashraf M, Zhao Y, Mukhtar MM, Rehman MU. Aspirin and immune system. *Int Immunopharmacol.* 2012 Jan;12(1):10-20. doi: 10.1016/j.intimp.2011.11.021. Epub 2011 Dec 13. PMID: 22172645.
18. Aspirin and inflammation. *Nat Struct Biol.* 1995 Aug;2(8):605-6. doi: 10.1038/nsb0895-605. PMID: 7552717.
19. Chiang N, Bermudez EA, Ridker PM, Hurwitz S, Serhan CN. Aspirin triggers antiinflammatory 15-epi-lipoxin A4 and inhibits thromboxane in a randomized human trial. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2004 Oct 19;101(42):15178-83. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0405445101. Epub 2004 Oct 7. PMID: 15471991; PMCID: PMC523452.
20. Compendium CH - Swiss central database.